

INFLUENCE OF INTERNET AVAILABILITY AND ACCESSIBILITY ON READING HABITS OF STUDENTS IN UNIVERSITY OF EDUCATION

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Abstract

This study investigated reading culture through internet availability, accessibility and use in a University of Education. Descriptive survey research design was adopted and the target population consisted of undergraduate students of Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State. Simple random sampling technique was employed to select two hundred (200) undergraduate students from the five colleges of the institution. The data were collected by administering a structured questionnaire and analysed using percentages and mean scores. The result of the study shows that internet availability and accessibility are still at low. Also, findings revealed that internet service in academic libraries of TASUED influences reading culture of students because it provides accurate contents of information needed; provides better information than print media in library; create acquisition of new knowledge; provides sense of values than textbooks; and helps in solving assignment online. Based on the result of this study, it was recommended that government should provide funds so as to make internet freely accessible to students using improvised password. This will enhance the easy use of internet, GSM phone and laptop computers for the promotion of reading culture among students of tertiary institutions across the nation.

Keywords: Accessibility Internet availability, reading habits, tertiary institution, undergraduates, university

Introduction

The achievement of quality education calls for the development of good reading habits of both young and adult learners. Reading is a key to a wealth of experience that links people in a way far beyond distance or time. Reading is important for students in general in order to acquire and cope with new knowledge in a changing world of technological age. It is important for self education and lifelong learning. (Kushmeeta and Rout 2013). The emergence of the internet has created an extraordinary change in all spheres of the society becoming one of the defining technologies of the digital age and global system. It is interconnected to computers and it provides many benefits to its users, including access to information from distant documents and databases that can be read and studied to prove knowledge (Emojorho, 2009). With the internet, students can improve their learning by gaining access to information and materials available on line can be read or down loaded and printed to read later. The internet is also not just a passive medium that students might explore to obtain information on their own. It is increasingly also being used by educational institutions and researchers as a flexible medium for delivering online education to distant or on campus students (Eden and Ofre, 2010).

Jackson (2011) remarked that the Internet will have great impact on education and learning if available to everywhere, and anytime, irrespective of gender, race/ethnicity, income or other socio-demographic characteristics. Thus, the Internet is a vital tool that will propel University education to greater heights as the world move further into the knowledge-based economy. Universities worldwide now invest a lot on internet access because it reduces the time between the production and utilisation of knowledge; improves co-operation and exchange of ideas with fellow researchers in other institutions, regions or countries, furthers the sharing of information; and promotes multidisciplinary research. The Internet has found useful applications in online data repositories, library catalogues, journals, news services, student and financial administration systems, online supported or solely online conducted teaching, as well as in digital communication with fellow students and lecturers. Other contemporary uses of Internet by students include purchasing, entertainment, and even dating. The investigation of how the internet fits into the daily life of staff and students at educational institutions is worthwhile when one considers the ubiquitous and all pervasive communications tool features of the internet (Williamson, 2008).

The internet is very useful to university students and staff in Nigeria because it enables them to have access to timely, accurate and relevant information that cannot be obtained from

library shelves. Cull (2011) noted that Internet searching helps university students to boost their intellectual development and job preparation. Due to the endless nature of information resources on the Internet, libraries are increasingly investing in provision of Internet services and resources to enable their clients have better access to the information. Reading makes way for a better understanding of one's own experiences and it can be an exciting voyage to self discovery. It is the art of interpreting printed and written words, the most effective process of conscious learning which influences the extent and accuracy of information, as well as the attitudes, morals, beliefs, judgment and action of readers (Alegbeleye, 2008).

However, Students' use of internet broadens knowledge by providing lots of materials from diverse sources which could be downloaded and printed later for reading. Meanwhile, these opportunities offered by ICTs, seems to discourage students from the use of printed information materials such as books, journals, magazines and etc (Edem & Ofre, 2010). Students might access the internet with the intention to search for useful information but may end up seeing an online caption with captivating photograph that will keep them hooked to the internet for hours; at the end they will discover that they have not read something useful.

Statement of Problem

Students nowadays, spend the better part of their time in school on one information technology device or the other such as laptops, desktops, palmtops, iPods, and blackberry. Mostly, they network socially with friends, reading dailies and rarely getting information in their various courses of study. The internet availability and accessibility on the other hands create problems to students as a result of power outage, the high cost of connectivity, low or poor connectivity, lack of ICT skills, interconnectivity problem, obsolete equipment, security and password which affects the information needs of its numerous users on daily basis. Therefore, this study sought to investigate students' reading habit through internet availability, accessibility and use in a University of Education.

Objective of the study

The objectives of this study are to:

1. determine the relationship between internet and reading habits of students in TASUED

2. determine the internet-related problems affecting students reading habits
3. examine the usefulness of internet to students in TASUED
4. examine the extent to which internet is available and accessible to undergraduate students of TASUED

Literature Reviews

Information and communication technologies as tools that have the potential to facilitate easy access to knowledge have been a welcomed development among academics and students. According to Adewuyi (2010) information and communication technologies is an electronic based technology that are used to store, process, and package information as well as provides access to knowledge. More also ICTs comprises of pieces of equipment, and networked infrastructure that are used for creating, manipulating, transferring and using information and knowledge (Aina, 2008).

Furthermore, in the past few years, information and communication technologies has provided society with a vast array of new communication capabilities, for instance, individuals can communicate real time with others in different locations using technologies such as instant messaging, voice over IP (VoIP) and video conferencing. Social networking websites like face book give users the opportunity of interacting with people around the world. Information explosion which have been associated with the emergence of sophisticated categories of ICTs devices that are manufactured with internet and Televisions facilities; have provided students with unrestricted access to knowledge and information beyond their imaginations (Chukwuma, 2011).

Palani (2012) is of the opinion that, effective reading is important avenue of effective learning and reading is interrelated with the total educational process and hence, educational success requires successful reading habit. He believes reading is the identification of the symbols and the association of appropriate meaning with them. It requires identification and comprehension. Comprehension skills help the learner to understand the meaning of words in isolation and in context.

Everyday reading consists of individuals' reading activities for a variety of purposes, such as for relaxation or information (Issa, 2012). They believes that from middle childhood through

adulthood, reading becomes a major component of studying, and much information learned through studying is initially acquired through reading. Thus everyday reading activities in which students engage may, considerably influence their studying skills and subsequent academic performance. There is a general sense in which one appreciates the link between good habits of reading and the academic performance of students generally, (Issa, 2012).

Singh (2011) examined academic achievement and study habits of higher secondary students. The study was conducted on hundred (100) higher secondary students randomly from two higher secondary schools. The result indicates that girls and boys differ significantly in their study habits and academic achievement. Bhan and Gupta (2010) on the other hand examined study habits and academic achievement among the students belonging to scheduled caste and non-scheduled caste group. The results revealed that sex has no significant impact on the study habits and academic achievement of students.

Ogbodo (2010) identifies three main types of reading habits. These are Hobby, Recreational and Concentration. A hobby is an activity one does because one derives some joy and satisfaction from doing it. After formal education's attainment, some people like reading as their hobby. Its purpose is to widen the reader's horizon areas like educational, religious, political, economic, current affairs, fiction and non-fiction. The practice of reading as a hobby helps one to be versatile in knowledge in many areas and the person can discuss issues knowledgeably with others.

Furthermore, reports have indicated that students are reading more books because of e-text; whether the digital software is on a handheld laptop or desktop computer, thousands of book titles have been transformed into digital books that can be read after being downloaded to the computer device (Houghton, 2010). The use of ICTs for reading, among students have broadened their horizon of academic opportunities and researches, enabling them to carry out their research, class assignments, write their examinations and share information resources with their counterpart all over the world. Fortunately, observation has shown that the use of modern day cable television has the potential to harness reading culture among students. It can provide university undergraduate students with television channels where discussion on educating literatures or book review can trigger curiosity for further reading of such book or books.

Internet

The term internet has been coined from a concept inter-networking that denotes interaction between networking of computers. It is an umbrella under which different networks, small and big, freely exchange information across the globe (Igbokwe, 2012). Internet, thus, can broadly be defined as worldwide network of computers communicating via an agreed upon protocol (rules for exchange of information). It provides access to the most diversified source of information hosted by individuals and various organisation worldwide on a vast network of servers (Habib, 2015). Internet gives on to the world web, the interconnections to thousands of servers created by various organisations, commercial establishments, industrial units, academic establishments, various groups, individuals. The web pages loaded on various servers provide variety of information in the form of text, graphics, animation, multimedia, etc. either free of cost or for a modest fee.

Reading Culture and Habit

The definition of reading has undergone through many improvements. Smith and Robinson (2010) define reading as a process for reader to understand a writer's message. A good reading habit is important for the development of personalities and mental capacities. This habit is necessary for a healthy intellectual growth and plays a very crucial role in enabling a person to achieve language proficiency (Popoola, 2010). Furthermore, an individual's interest to read is determined by the considerable extent of the amount and intensity of pursuing the reading activity. By reading books frequently and having a good reading habit, the reader is able analyze other's idea, which makes one think more critically. Reading provides readers with great knowledge, understanding and a sense of values, which enable them gradually to develop the greatest of all virtues and the ability to understand other people beliefs (Ogbodo, 2010).

Reading culture is the key-stone upon which the lives of some eminent successful personalities and students are laid in order to sustain lifelong learning. Great minds have made impact on the world through reading culture which they developed as important part of their routine activity without which they feel unaccomplished for the day (Akinbola, 2007).

Magara and Batambuze (2005) opined that a reading culture means that reading is part of a specific culture and a habit that is shared and highly valued by a society. It is valued in the sense that it is considered important in order to gain the information which is needed for everyday life. In support Gabriel, Basse and Randy (2004) note that reading culture is the stage where reading

becomes a complete self-directed pleasurable activity, whose goal is to engender lifelong love for reading, fully internalized as a habit and a means of relaxation, culminating into life-long learning. University undergraduate students must inculcate reading as part of their value system in order to be adjudged as people that have reading culture.

Promoting Reading Culture through Internet Availability, Accessibility and Use in a University of Education

Internet has become a part of library environment today. It has added a great value to the academic library and information services. According to Neena (2001) with the expansion of internet a new class of electronic document has emerged, it was at once promising and attractive for its obvious advantage of speed and transmissibility and profoundly elusive and confounding to the library community because of its intangibility and malleability. The internet has become global and ubiquitous and it reaches in hundreds of countries of all continents and is featured daily in the business sections of all major newspapers.

Internet is playing an important role in transforming the library system and the way in which we view the library resources and the library services. With the help of web based library services in developed countries, users are attended round the clock. Internet provides links to various library sites, specializing in almost every topic and they can be accessed directly from any part of the world. As the libraries are going web based more and more libraries' are becoming accessible via libraries' web pages. With an internet connection, a student in any university of Nigeria can browse through the documents in computers of National libraries or elsewhere in the globe.

Internet has thus integrated nearly all library activities e-mail, discussion through listserves, support reference service through search of remote databases, exploiting the catalogue of other institutions, participation in inter-library loan (ILL), ordering books and journals, inter-library loan establishing home page, etc. Under these circumstances resource sharing and cooperative functioning of the libraries through internet has also become vital. The utilisation of facilities by them largely depend on getting internet connection and exploiting its services and resources for providing better access to global information (Habib, 2015). Attainment of undergraduate permanent literacy can be done through reading. Different library resources - books, magazines, journals, audiovisuals etc provide different information. The library has to provide sufficiently,

good resources to complement qualitative education. These resources can take children and youth far above technical literacy to developing reading culture which makes permanent literacy attainable (Aina, 2013).

The more a student reads, the more knowledge is gathered which will eventually equip him with the necessary potentials to achieve personal goals. This in line with the words of Sahepty (2011) that having reading culture can stimulate a university undergraduate student to be creative and innovative because innovation originate from combination of ideas and concepts. When university undergraduate students have good reading culture, the potential and ability to move themselves and the nation forward is high. Furthermore, Nortija as quoted by Kon 2012 asserts that reading culture create among students the development of fully literate society with taste for knowledge which will lead to building a knowledgeable and informed society. Furthermore, reading culture is highly considered necessary for university undergraduate students to be able to acquire the necessary knowledge that is needed for them to effect development and growth in the society. In support, Kazim (2012) assert that when the mind is developed, the society stands a better chance of also being developed. Furthermore, Abdullahi (2011) opined that reading culture is a necessary prerequisite that is needed in order for Nigerian university undergraduate students to broaden their minds and expand their horizon. For instance some university undergraduate students seem to have low intelligent quotient and not able to defend their certificates because they lack basic reading culture which equips the mind with the necessary knowledge to face the future after graduation from school.

The success of university undergraduate students' career during school and after graduation is anchored on the possession of proper reading culture. In support, Kitabu (2011) asserts that students must cultivate reading culture for their personal and career development since reading books equips people with knowledge and power. Furthermore, he asserts that reading culture has crucial role to play in creating independent learners, underpinning literacy skills and educational attainment; helping people to have better understanding of themselves as well as others. Meanwhile, there are challenges and problems that are associated with reading culture due to several internal and external factors that are inherent within the individual and the society respectively.

The immature character of some undergraduate students which leads them to use the internet without discipline serves as source of distraction while browsing the internet. In support,

Adegbeji as quoted by Edem and Ofre (2010) asserts that there is potential among less mature undergraduate students, for conflict between the time and effort devoted by them to positive educational uses of the ICTs such as information browsing, communication and study; and other less educational uses such as entertainment and pleasure seeking and antisocial behavior. Furthermore, the contemporary students as compared before are more exposed to different types of media particularly on television; they spend most of their time in front of television sets rather than reading their books and working on their assignments (Ferri, 2009).

More so, Onovughe (2012) opined that contemporary students spend the better part of their time in school on one information technology device or the other such as laptops, desktops, palmtops, iPods, iPod Touch, ipad from Apple and blackberry, DVD player etc. She further stated that on close enquiry, one usually finds out that they are networking socially with friends, reading dailies, and rarely getting information on their various courses. It is rather unfortunate that there is no close monitored censorship in Nigeria on the use of dangerous website by students; the future implication on the educational system is better imagined than experienced.

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Furthermore, Studies have shown that general news headline and the summary of news and events can contribute positively to reading culture by triggering the interest of students to purchase the newspaper for full details of the content of such information material (Mbah, 2010). Also, university undergraduate students in the course of their academic works may find it easier to locate, evaluate and collect information from variety of sources through the use of ICTs. ICTs is defined for the purpose of this study as diverse sets of modern electronic and technological tools and

devices used to create, collate, store, exchange, manage and provide access to recorded information and knowledge (Onovughe, 2012).

Methodology

The research design for this study is descriptive survey. The study was carried out in Tai Solarin University of Education. The population of this study consists of undergraduate students of Tai Solarin University of Education during the 2016/2017 academic session. Simple random sampling technique was used to select the participants from five colleges in the university. The colleges are: COSIT (7 Departments), COSMAS (5 Departments), COVTED (6 Departments), COSPED (5 Departments) and COHUM (7 Departments). The instrument for data collection for this study was a questionnaire, titled “Scale on Reading Habit, Internet Availability and Accessibility” (SRHIAA). The questionnaire was administered personally to ensure excellent response rate as well as to avoid any misunderstanding while providing responses. The data were analysed using percentages and mean scores

Presentation and Data Analysis

Table 1: Demographic information

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	94	47%
Female	106	53%
Level of Study		
100 level	30	15%
200 level	52	26%
300 level	48	24%
400 level	70	35%
Total	200	100%

Table 1 reveals that 94(47%) of the respondents were male while 106(53%) were female. Also, 15% of the respondents were 100 level students, 26% of the respondents were 200 level students while 24% of the respondents were 300 level students and 35% of the respondents were 400 level students. Majority of the respondents were also found to be in their fourth year of study.

Table 2: Extent to which Internet is available to undergraduate students in TASUED

Internet Availability	Frequency	Percentage
Very Available	98	49%
Slightly Available	84	42%
Not Available	18	9%
Total	200	100

Table 2 above show the availability of internet services in TASUED, 49% of the respondents admitted that internet is very much available, also, 42% of the respondents opined that the internet was slightly available while 9% of the respondents stated that the internet is not available.

Table 3: Extent of internet accessibility in TASUED

Internet Accessibility	Frequency	Percentage
Very accessible	34	17%
Slightly accessible	46	23%
Not accessible	120	60%
Total	120	100

Table 3 above shows the level of internet accessibility in TASUED, 17% of the respondents agreed that internet is very accessible; in addition, 23% of the respondents revealed that the internet is slightly accessible while 60% of the respondents admitted that the internet is not accessible.

Figure 1: Usefulness of internet by undergraduate students in TASUED

Figure 1 above shows the purpose of using internet by survey undergraduate in TASUED. 13% of the respondents used internet for academic/course work. 12% of the respondents used internet for completion of assignment, in addition, 9% of the respondents used internet for research purpose, also, 23% of the respondents used internet for group discussion /chatting with friends, meanwhile 6% of the respondents used internet to seek for project material, however, 15% of the respondents used internet for personal knowledge and 21% of the respondents used internet for entertainment.

Table 4: Internet-related problems affecting reading habits in TASUED

Challenges	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
Time constraints	98 49%	72 36%	16 8%	14 7%	3.	Accept
Power failure	105 52.5%	66 33%	13 6.5%	16 8%	3.3	Accept
Poor internet services	89 44.5%	96 48%	6 3%	9 5%	3.3	Accept
Social services restriction	97 48.5%	79 39.5%	14 7%	10 5%	3.3	Accept
Lack of technical know-how	123 61.5%	58 29%	11 5.5%	8 4%	3.5	Accept
Technology constraints	93 46.5%	84 42%	16 8%	7 3.5%	3.3	Accept

Eye discomfort through reading with Internet	107 55.5%	69 34.5%	13 6.5%	11 3.5%	3.4	Accept
Hastening while reading with Internet because of unlimited access time	123 61.5%	58 29%	10 5%	9 4.5%	3.5	Accept
Unwanted activities from Internet	129 64.5%	44 22%	17 8.5%	10 5%	3.5	Accept

Table 4 above shows the problems affecting the use of internet in reading in TASUED. Respondents accept that time constraints associates with the use of internet in TASUED with mean score of 3.2, also the respondents accept that power failure inhibit the utilization of internet with mean rate of 3.3, in addition, respondents accept that poor internet services discourage the use of internet with mean rate of 3.3, moreover, findings shows that social services restriction inhibit the use of internet in TASUED with mean rate of 3.3. Thus, responses of the respondents agreed that lack of technical know-how affect the use of internet with mean rate of 3.5, however, the mean rate of 3.3 shows that respondents accept that technology constraints obstruct the use of internet, meanwhile, 3.4 mean rate shows that the respondents accept that eye discomfort through reading internet create a challenge. Also, findings shows that respondents accept that hastening while reading with Internet because of unlimited access time create a barrier for internet use with mean rate of 3.5 while mean rate of 3.5 shows that the respondents accept that unwanted activities on internet obstruct the effective reading with internet in TASUED.

Table 5: The influences of internet on reading habit of students in TASUED

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
Using internet in reading provide accurate contents of information need than using textbooks	112 56%	74 37%	10 5%	4 2%	3.5	Accept
Using internet in reading provide better information than print media in library	126 63%	62 61.5%	8 4%	4 2%	3.5	Accept
The use of internet in reading create acquisition of new knowledge and skills	102 51%	76 38%	12 6%	10 5%	3.6	Accept
Information gaining through internet provides my reading culture with a sense of values than textbooks	128 64%	60 30%	6 3%	6 3%	3.4	Accept

Using internet in reading helps in solving assignment online	132 66%	62 31%	2 1%	4 2%	3.6	Accept
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Table 5 above shows the influences of internet on reading culture of students in TASUED, the responses of the respondents with mean rate of 3.5 accept that using internet in reading provide accurate contents of information need than using textbooks, furthermore, the response of the respondents indicated that using internet in reading provide better information than print media in library with mean score of 3.5. In addition, the men rate of 3.6 shows that the use of internet in library create acquisition of new knowledge and skills in reading. Also, respondents accept that information gaining through internet provides their reading culture with a sense of values than textbooks which mount for 3.4 mean score. Lastly, the respondents are of opinion that using internet in reading helps in solving assignment online with mean rate of 3.6 respectively.

Conclusion

Internet availability and accessibility are indispensable tools for the success of every academic endeavour in the contemporary age of information and technology revolution. The reading culture of Nigerian students and the educational sector in general can be enhanced via the provision of the necessary resources that will assist students to appreciate the unrestricted access to knowledge that comes with information and communication technologies. Based on reviewed and findings, this study conclude that internet utilization and access is still at low ebb and some universities do not have all the necessary infrastructures/facilities for the Internet. The situation is pathetic because of some numerous problems including erratic power supply, out-dated equipment, connectivity and maintenance cost etc. The internet provides a wealth of information. Students are using the internet significantly and it occupies an important place among various information sources. Reading and academic achievement are essential which help the undergraduate in obtaining meaningful and desirable knowledge. Good reading culture act is a strong weapon for the students to excel in life.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were made:-

- i. The government should provide funds so as to make internet freely accessible to students using improvised password, this will enhance the easy use of internet, GSM phone and Laptop computers for the promotion of reading culture among students of tertiary institutions across the nation.
- ii. Academic libraries should provide the enabling environment to enhance effective use of internet facilities.
- iii. Students should be encouraged to spend more time to read by including reading hour into course outline.
- iv. More so, students should exercise caution and discipline themselves while using ICTs by resisting the pressure to open destructive websites. This will help them to avoid the adverse influences exerted by ICTs on reading culture.
- v. Proper training of internet use should be provided to the undergraduate students to accelerate access to different electronic sources of information and support their academic activities.
- vi. University of Education should have centralized internet servers that will function for 24 hours facilities such as generating set, solar system, should be acquired and put in place to ensure smooth using of the Internet by the academics.
- vii. More funds should be made available by the authorities of the institutions under study for running and maintaining the Internet facilities.
- viii. Lastly, university management should provide convenient reading space, well - structured sitting arrangement and well illuminated area in the library for undergraduate

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